

Recasting Sedition in Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023 – Abolishing or Reinforcing Colonial Sedition Law in India?

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Abstract:

It is a classic theory of democracy in political science that the governments instituted among men derive all just power from the consent of the governed, and may, therefore, be by them at any time altered, amended or abolished. In the light of this theory, it is a settled principle that freedom of speech and expression includes expressing dissent against established government. So far as India is concerned, Art. 19(1)(a) of the Constitution of India protects freedom of speech and expression of its citizens provided reasonable restrictions can be imposed by law under Art. 19(2). But this is post-constitutional position. A pre-constitutional statutory provision in Indian Penal Code (IPC) has come in conflict with Art. 19(1)(a) time and again and i.e. Section 124A which provided for Law of sedition. Presently, cases pending under this section are been put on abeyance by apex court in *SG Vombatkere v. Union of India* (2022) and no new case can be filed under this section since central government is reviewing this law. Sedition can be explained as any action or speech that leads to revolt against the authority of the State. Law of sedition was included by British Parliament in IPC to curb Wahabi movement in the year 1870. Currently, Section 152 of Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023 includes provision similar to erstwhile sedition law under the heading 'Acts endangering sovereignty unity and integrity of India'. Looking at the legislative intention behind inserting law of sedition in IPC, the question arises as to the justification to existence and continuance of this law of sedition in present legal system. The aim of present research is to analyze that legislative intention and to find out whether new Section 152 is 'old wine in new bottle'.

Keywords- Sedition, Freedom of speech and expression, Indian Penal Code, Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, Legislative Intention

Introduction

"The section 124-A, under which I am happily charged, is perhaps the prince among the political sections of the Indian Penal Code designed to suppress the liberty of the citizen."

Mahatma Gandhi

"Affection cannot be manufactured or regulated by law. If one has no affection for a person or system one should be free to give the fullest expression to his disaffection, so long as he does not contemplate, promote, or incite violence. But the section under which [I am charged] is one under which mere promotion of disaffection is a crime. I have studied some of the cases tried under it, and I know that some of the most loved of India's patriots have been convicted under it. I consider it a privilege, therefore to be charged under that section. ... I have no personal ill will against any single administrator; much less can I have any disaffection towards the King's person. But I hold it to be a virtue to be disaffected towards a Government which, in its totality, has done more harm to India than any previous system. India is less manly under the British rule than she ever was before. Holding such a belief I consider it to be a sin to have affection for the system." Gandhi's comments elevated dissension and sedition—both of which have historically been associated with violence and terror—to a new plane of nonviolence and political legality.

Sedition can be explained as any action or speech that leads to revolt against the authority of the State. Law of sedition was included by British Parliament in IPC to curb Wahabi movement in the year 1870. Currently, Section 152 of Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023 includes provision similar to erstwhile sedition law under the heading 'Acts endangering sovereignty unity and integrity of India'. Looking at the legislative intention behind inserting law of sedition in IPC, the question arises as to the justification to existence and continuance of this law of sedition in present legal system. The objective of present research was to analyze that legislative intention and to find out whether new Section 152 is 'old wine in new bottle' or innovation in Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita.

From Savarkar's call for armed rebellion to Gandhian non-violent non-cooperation, the colonial state's response to revolutionary nationalism in India gave rise to two primary colonial weapons against all anti-colonial nationalism. The first weapon was surveillance, a newly developed state control technique that subjected a growing number of young revolutionaries to regular observation. Sedition legislation was the colonial state of India's second, and possibly more significant, weapon. Carrying on with this line of reasoning would be mistaking the symptom for the cause. The true threat did not lie in weapons and explosives or in anarchy or nihilism. Indian discontent with colonial rule was the cause.

In essence, sedition is an offense against the state's security. It describes speaking or writing in a way that incites hatred or disdain for the sovereign state, incites disloyalty toward the Constitution or the democratically elected government, or makes an illegal endeavor to bring about a change in the government. Sedition has traditionally been justified on the grounds that a sovereign government has the right to resist both external and internal aggression, and to protect the citizens of the state from harm. A seditious intention, according to English law, means 'an intention to bring into hatred or contempt, or to excite disaffection against, the king or the Government and Constitution of the United Kingdom, or either House of Parliament, or the administration of justice; or to excite the King's subjects to attempt otherwise than by lawful means, the alteration of any matter in Church or State by law established; or to incite persons to commit any crime in general disturbance of the peace; or to raise discontent or disaffection among His Majesty's subjects; or to promote feelings of ill-will and hostility between different classes of His Majesty's subjects.'

From their inception, laws suppressing dissent have been political in nature. The earliest known such decree was under The First Statute of Westminster, 1275, which came into being as a direct outcome of a 'rebellion of the barons' against the monarch who was considered 'the holder of the Divine Right'. This was aimed at safeguarding the ruling establishment, including the nobility, from popular uprisings that challenged the existing order. The doctrine of *Scandalum Magnatum* meaning 'scandal of the magnates' became the basis for this law, which placed curbs on scandalizing or criticizing royalty, judges or peers. According to the thirty fourth chapter of the First Statute: *'none be so hardy to tell or publish any false news or tales, whereby discord, or occasion of discord or slander may grow between the King and his people, or the great men of the realm.'*

Over the subsequent centuries this made its journey through the Statutes of Treason (1352 and 1534) and evolved into the offence of seditious libel in 1606 at a Star Chamber decision in *de Libellis Famosis*, the law of libel or written defamation. In this case, the court held that criticism of public officials and the government would inculcate disrespect for public authority. Interestingly, this case evaded some of the safeguards laid down in the offences of Treason and *candalum Magnatum*. Hamburger points out that the 18th century saw the increased usage of sedition against the printed word.

In *Dombrowski v. Pfister*, the US Supreme Court, while hearing a petition from James Dombrowski seeking relief from prosecution under Louisiana's Subversive Activities and Communist Control Law, invoked the overbreadth doctrine,

wherein "a regulation of speech can sweep too broadly and prohibit protected as well as non-protected speech" and discussed the need to protect the First Amendment rights from a 'chilling effect'. The court said:

"A chilling effect upon First Amendment rights might result from such prosecution regardless of its prospects of success or failure, as is indicated by appellants' representations of the actions taken under the statutes. Although sedition survives as an offence in the US, it is very narrowly construed and can even said to have fallen in disuse."

Genesis and evolution of Sedition Law in India:

Thomas Macaulay, a British historian and politician, authored the sedition statute in 1837. It was placed into the IPC as Section 124A in 1870, ten years after its enactment. Law academics argue that this clause was included in the IPC to prevent the burgeoning revolt led by Deobandi scholars to topple British rule in India. The rebellious movement was also known as the Wahabi Movement. Since then, it has been employed by all governments to silence anyone who criticizes official policy. The provision was later amended in 1870 and was based on the English Treason Felony Act of 1848, which dealt with dissent, mutinous acts, and rebellions. This law was used by the British administrators against Mahatma Gandhi, Lokmanya Tilak, Bhagat Singh, Maulana Azad, Annie Besant and Jawaharlal Nehru for their speeches, writings and actions during the freedom struggle. Bal Gangadhar Tilak was charged with sedition twice, once in 1897 for his speech in Shivaji Park, Bombay, which led to the killing of two British officials, and the second time in 1908, when he was arrested for his seditious writings against the British in the Marathi newspaper 'Kesari' wherein on both occasions he was convicted by the Bombay High Court.

During the Constituent Assembly Debates in April 1947, Vallabhbhai Patel suggested an exception for "seditious" language, stating that it should be treated differently from other speech rights. Following more discussion, the Constituent Assembly rejected this idea in 1948 based on a suggestion made by K.M. Munshi, who emphasized the provision's colonial origins and its history of being used to hinder the independence movement. The prominent Congressman and educationist KM Munshi vehemently expressed during his time in the Constituent Assembly that he believed the Indian Constitution ought to allow for a certain amount of sedition. The framers of our Constitution recognized that sedition laws could have a negative impact on the right to free speech and expression.

Despite not being included in the Constitution, sedition remained illegal and was classified as a crime under Section 124A of the IPC. The purpose of this move was to prevent any such

behavior that would jeopardize the peace and order in a civil society. To preserve the democratic administration that had been duly elected, Section 124A was required. This component had to be kept in place as well, given the expanding separatist movements that emerged in the nation following its independence. The general populace needed to be made to fear that disobedience to the government could result in harsh penalties. However, the Coroners and Justice Act, 2009 asserts that sedition has been outlawed in the United Kingdom, which served as the model for Indian legislation.

Judicial Perspective over Law of Sedition in Post-constitutional Era:

After the commencement of Constitution of India, in various cases people were accused and convicted under sedition law. But in the landmark decision of the Indian Supreme Court in *Kedar Nath Singh v. State of Bihar*, the judicial controversy regarding the validity of section 124-A of the Indian Penal Code, 1860, was resolved and Court pointed towards one of the basic problems involved in India in the enforcement of fundamental rights. Fundamental rights, guaranteed in the Constitution, have to be applied within a legal system devised originally by an alien government with an object which is no longer valid in the present-day context. The result, therefore, is that there often arises a conflict between the rights and the pre-Constitution laws still in force, and the courts are called upon to decide the validity of such laws under psychologically different and entirely changed socio-economic urges and conditions. This was precisely the problem before the Supreme Court in this case. In this case, the appellant was charged with having 'brought or attempted to bring into hatred or contempt or excited or attempted to excite disaffection towards the Government' by having delivered certain speeches and was thereupon convicted under section 124-A of the IPC by a Magistrate's court in the State of Bihar. The appellant's conviction having been sustained by the Patna High Court, he obtained special leave to appeal to the Supreme Court. The main argument for the appellant was that section 124-A of the Penal Code was repugnant to the provisions of Art. 19 of the Constitution guaranteeing freedom of speech and expression. The point at issue, therefore, was whether the restrictions imposed by S. 124-A were within the ambit of permissible legislative power under article 19(2). The answer to the question depended upon the acceptance of either of the two divergent interpretations given to section 124-A in the pre-Constitution days. In the *Kedar Nath* case, the Supreme Court relied upon the narrower of the two interpretations and thereby came to the conclusion that the impugned section imposes 'restrictions on the fundamental freedom of speech and expression, but these restrictions cannot but be

said to be in the interest of public order and within the ambit of permissible legislative interference with the fundamental right.' The judgment has far-reaching implications on the scope of liberty of speech.

However, Justice P.B. Sinha, clarified that criticism of the government did not amount to sedition unless it was accompanied by an incitement or call for violence. Some have argued that the Court in *Kedar Nath* did not provide direction about who decides if there is an incitement to violence. In 2021, the two-Judge Bench of the Supreme Court quashed the sedition FIR filed against late journalist Vinod Dua for his comments on the Prime Minister's handling of the COVID-19 crisis. Justice U.U. Lalit held that while Dua had criticised the government, his comments could not be termed as seditious. In its Judgment in this case, the Court reiterated its earlier decision in *Kedar Nath*, but refused to constitute a screening committee as this would breach the legislature's powers.

On May 1, 2023, the Centre informed the Supreme Court that the legislative process of reviewing the sedition law was in the final stages, adding the government is keen on pushing reforms and that something may be in works as early as the coming monsoon session of Parliament (July-August). The submission prompted the court to defer the judicial determination of the validity of the controversial law until the second week of August. Meanwhile, the Law Commission came out with the 279th report, dated 24 May 2023, as it answered a reference on the sedition law made to the panel in March 2016 by the Union home ministry and it recommended that the colonial law be retained. This is, however, not the first time that the Commission has scrutinized the usage of Section 124A of IPC. Earlier 39th, 42nd and 267th Report (1968) also analyzed sedition law in India. The panel mentioned statistics on deaths of security forces and civilians due to insurgency, militancy and terrorism in various states, including Chhattisgarh (Maoist violence), the North-East states and Jammu & Kashmir, to emphasise that India's internal security must be shielded to enable it to exercise its sovereignty and protect its territorial integrity.

The order of the Supreme Court of India in *S.G. Vombatkere v. Union of India* has been monumental for the future of dissent in the country. The order has been passed in a bunch of petitions filed challenging the Constitutionality of the provision on sedition under the Indian Penal Code 1860 ("IPC"). During the hearings in the matter, the Union of India, in its affidavit, averred that it had decided to reexamine and reconsider the provisions on sedition under the IPC. It was further submitted by the Union of India that the Supreme Court may examine the constitutional validity of the law on sedition once the exercise of reconsideration has

been undertaken by the government. Accordingly, the Court deemed it inappropriate to use the provisions on sedition till the reexamination by the Union of India is complete. Additionally, the Court recommended that the governments should restrain from registering any FIR, or undertaking any coercive measure in sedition cases till the matter is under consideration. The Court also ordered that all pending proceedings concerning sedition would be kept in abeyance.

Change in Law of Sedition by Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita:

BNS has omitted S. 124A of IPC under which sedition was punishable offence and replaced it with treason under S. 152. A key change in Section 152 is to remove an old provision in which a person convicted of sedition could get away with a fine. Section 152 of the bill prescribes imprisonment for life or imprisonment which may extend to seven years, in addition to the fine, as punishment. So, in a way, punishment has been made more severe. The name sedition law has also gone away. Words “disaffection towards the Government established by law in India” have been removed from S. 152. It directly targets secessionism, separatism, and a call for armed rebellion – words like “contempt” or “hatred” against the Government of India removed. It also includes “electronic communication” and “use of financial means” as tools for perpetuating an act “endangering sovereignty, unity and integrity of India.” Earlier sedition law required very harsh words and some action like an example of uprising against the country. Under Section 152, merely words by themselves will attract the charge of having participated in anti-national activities. Terrorism offences, organized crimes and criminal activities added in the new provision.

But this new provision also suffers with certain loopholes. Instead of making incitement to violence or disruption to public order a condition precedent to invoke the charges, the proposed Section 152 continues to criminalize any act that “excites or attempts to excite” secessionist activities or “encourages feelings of separatist activities” and also penalizes a person who “indulges in or commits any such act”, vesting with law enforcement agencies a greater discretion to decide what can be brought within the fold of an act “endangering sovereignty, unity and integrity of India” for the purposes of slapping the charges. Section 152 takes in its purview almost everything, including a speech, a newspaper article, a book, a drama– everything that Section 124A of IPC currently penalizes as sedition.

Conclusion and suggestions:

According to a number of publications, India has filed about 800 sedition lawsuits against over 13,000 individuals since 2010. According to the “Crime in India 2020” report from the National

Crime Records Bureau, there were 70, 93, and 73 instances of sedition in 2018, 2019, and 2020, respectively. Sedition cases have increased, but conviction rates have remained low. In 2014, there was one conviction out of 47 cases that were registered; in 2015, there were zero convictions out of 30 cases that were registered; in 2016, there was one conviction out of 35 cases that were registered; in 2017, there was one conviction out of 51 cases that were registered; in 2018, there was one conviction out of 70 cases that were registered; and in 2019, there was one conviction out of 93 cases that were registered. The low conviction rates show that Section 124A is being misused and that cases are being brought even when the necessary ingredients are missing. Under the provision, a number of journalists, artists, and dissidents have been unsuccessfully booked. For example, Binayak Sen, an Adivasi activist and doctor, was accused of sedition on the grounds that he had books written by the Naxals. Aseem Trivedi was also charged with sedition after he made remarks about the nation’s corruption and immoral bureaucracy.

The colonial law has remained a useful instrument for the police and other state agencies to instill fear in the populace and quell any valid critiques or opposition against the governments ever since the sedition law was enacted. Although the misuse of the law has been a feature of all succeeding regimes, in recent years it has become more overt. A quick look at the instances that have been filed recently shows how the law is being abused more and more. Two dozen sedition cases against prominent participants in the Citizenship Amendment Act, 2019 (CAA) protests, twenty-seven cases pertaining to the Pulwama tragedy, and twenty-two cases pertaining to the reporting of the Hathras gang-rape incident were filed, according to the portal. Seditious actions can include everything from merely displaying signs to displaying anti-government phrases and private on social media.

India is home to the world’s largest democracy, and democracy requires the freedom of speech and expression. Democracy is dependent on dissent. If the government receives comments at the appropriate moment, a great deal of resources, government equipment, etc., can be saved. On the other hand, polarizing forces must be restrained in order to protect national integrity. The majority of the criticism directed towards the Sedition can be eliminated by simply preventing its improper enforcement and misuse. The government needs to give that top priority. In this way, new S. 152 of Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita can be stopped from misuse otherwise it will only reinforce colonial sedition law in India and as Gandhiji said will continue to suppress liberties of people.

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